

METHODOLOGY APPENDIX FOR “AN EQUITABLE PHASE OUT OF FOSSIL FUEL EXTRACTION”

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INTRODUCTION

This document serves to describe the methodology employed in the 2023 report by the Civil Society Equity Review entitled “An Equitable Phase Out of Fossil Fuel Extraction: Towards a Reference Framework for a Fast and Fair Rapid Global Phase Out of Coal, Oil and Gas” (Civil Society Equity Review 2023)¹. Specifically, these methods are used in calculating the equitable phase-out timelines as well as the provision and receipt of financial support to implement these phase-out timelines.

This document provides additional information about the rationale of certain methodological decisions that go beyond the level of detail in the report, provides additional background data on some of the indicators used, details our data sources and describes their limitations, and describes the formulas used for the calculations. While many of these methodological choices were made on purely technical grounds, others are inherently normative. For key normatively salient choices, the underlying ethical issues were explained to and discussed with our civil society partners, and the equity-related choices were clarified, deliberated, and resolved in a manner that the partners agreed were consistent with their ethical positions, and this analysis was implemented in accordance with those choices. In the case of less critical choices that still had some degree of normative relevance, the technical team implemented choices that most consistently reflected the CSO partner’s underlying principles. This appendix focuses primarily on technical aspects, with a reminder of normative elements where relevant, which are addressed in greater detail in the main report.

THE DEPENDENCE INDICATOR

A key aspect of our equitable fossil phaseout framework is how much countries depend on fossil fuel extraction. Countries that are more dependent on extraction will need more time for the phaseout in order to enable a just transition. In defining dependence, this framework focuses on elements that entail social harms if the phaseout is too fast.

For this analysis, we measure national dependence on fossil fuel extraction via a composite measure with three elements, reflecting different ways that economies and societies rely on fossil fuels: 1. for domestic energy supplies, 2. for government revenues, and 3. for jobs. The rationale for each of these elements is explained on pages 19 to 21 of the main report. For each of oil, gas, and coal, for each country, these three elements are then weighted and summed, and the sum is then scaled according to the country’s capacity to manage and overcome its dependence.

Note that we assess dependence aggregated at the national level, rather than focusing on subnational variations. Thus, for example, provincial oil revenues are counted towards the national total, and assessed in proportion to the total of all national and state/provincial revenues, rather than assessing each state/province’s oil revenues as a share of its own total revenues. We focus on national totals because they can be expected to play a key role in the delivery of the *intranational* means of implementation that can make an equitable phaseout possible, for example by providing finance to their fossil-fuel-dependent states and provinces – wealthy (high-capacity) countries will be better able to do this than low-capacity countries.

The following subsections outline:

- The methods and sources we use to measure three elements of dependence;
- How we weight and sum these three elements;
- How we scale the dependence indicator in relation to capacity;
- Aspects of dependence that we do not (currently) consider in our framework;
- The specific quantified elements of dependence for all countries assessed.

¹ <https://equityreview.org/extraction-equity-2023>

DEFINING THREE ELEMENTS OF DEPENDENCE

DEPENDENCE ON DOMESTIC FOSSIL FUELS AS A SOURCE OF ENERGY SUPPLY:

The first element of the composite measure of dependence reflects dependence on domestically produced energy resources for meeting domestic energy needs. It is defined as the share of primary energy consumption that is met from domestically-sourced fossil fuels. Specifically, this is a country's fossil fuel production minus its exports, divided by total primary energy consumption. In this report, we are using 2022 data obtained from the Energy Institute's Statistical Review of World Energy 2023 (Energy Institute 2023a, 2023b).

DEPENDENCE ON GOVERNMENT REVENUES FROM FOSSIL FUELS:

The second element reflects the dependence on extracted fossil fuels for generating revenue to meet public needs. It is defined as the share of government revenues that comes from oil and gas. In this report, we are using 2021 figures. Revenues from coal are orders of magnitude smaller than from oil and gas, and so are not included in our measure. Therefore, this element is treated as zero for coal, a choice that may be revisited in updated version of this analysis if data availability allows. Any dependence on coal revenues occurs mostly at the subnational level (some provincial governments do rely on coal revenue), but this level of detail is beyond the scope of our framework.

For most countries, we use the full set of government revenues from oil and gas extraction, including taxes, royalties, profit sharing etc. For the United States and Canada, unlike most other countries, taxes on oil companies are not recorded as oil revenues in published government data; in these cases, our figure relates to royalties only.

For countries with significant levels of dependence (most of the countries in our study), data are taken from Article IV reports (periodic reviews of countries' financial and economic situation) published by the International Monetary Fund (IMF 2023). These reports sometimes state the share of revenues derived just from oil, and sometimes from oil and gas combined; we assume that where only oil revenues are stated, the revenues from gas are too small to be reported. For less-dependent countries, the IMF does not include revenue dependence in its reports; in these cases, we use government statistics, at both national and (where appropriate, in federal systems) subnational level, reports of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI), or secondary sources. The specific sources for each country are listed in Table 1.

We assume that revenues are divided between oil and gas in proportion to the relative production volumes of each, expressed in energy terms.

Where data were cited by fiscal year, we use the 2020/21 fiscal year data for 2021. For Azerbaijan, Egypt, and Ghana, for which the most recent Article IV reports were published during 2021, we use the projection for the full year. For a small number of countries, 2021 data were not available. Since 2020 data would be distorted by impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic, in these cases we use data from 2019 (Australia, Brazil, Chad, China, Congo, Russia, Sudan) or 2018 (Iran). For Venezuela, we have data only for 2023.

DEPENDENCE ON FOSSIL FUEL JOBS:

The third element of the composite measure of dependence reflects the dependence on the fossil fuel production sector for employment. It is defined as the share of the total workforce employed in fossil fuel extraction. We use the IEA's World Energy Employment report (IEA 2022), which gives oil and gas extraction and coal mining job numbers for India, China, Other Asia Pacific, Africa, North America, Central & South America, Europe and Rest of World in 2019. For each multi-country region, we assume that job numbers are distributed between countries in proportion to their share of that region's production (of either coal or oil & gas), and that oil & gas jobs (which are combined in the data) are shared between oil and gas in proportion to their production in terms of energy content.² The data include both direct extraction jobs and indirect

² We use this source for employment data, and rely on the stated assumptions of distribution between countries and between fuel types, because (to our knowledge) disaggregated country data are not available at sufficient resolution. For example, International Labour Organisation data on employment by sector do not disaggregate beyond the 'Mining and quarrying' sector. The disaggregation key (extraction volumes for each fuel, measured in terms of embodied energy) is obtained from the Statistical Review of World Energy 2023 (Energy Institute 2023a, 2023b).

jobs in sectors that specifically supply fossil fuel extraction activities, but not indirect jobs in production of general goods and services used in extraction, such as cement and steel. We divide this number of jobs by the total size of the workforce in the country, using data from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (World Bank 2023). The workforce is the total economically active population i.e. those of working age, whether formally employed, informally employed or unemployed.

Country	Scope of fossil revenues	Source ³
Algeria	Hydrocarbons	IMF Article IV report, February 2023, p.5
Angola	Oil	IMF Article IV report, March 2023, p.5
Argentina	Hydrocarbons	EITI (2023: Table 30)
Australia	Petroleum	Burke (2023)
Azerbaijan	Oil	IMF Article IV report, December 2021, p.35
Bolivia	Hydrocarbon-related	IMF Article IV report, November 2022, p.5
Brazil	Oil and gas	Laan and Maino (2022)
Brunei	Oil and gas	IMF Article IV report, September 2022, p.5
Cameroon	Oil	IMF Article IV report, March 2022, p.43
Canada	Oil and gas royalties (federal and provincial)	Statistics Canada (2022a, 2022b)
Chad	Oil	IMF Article IV report, July 2019, p.7
China	Oil and gas: corporate income tax, SOE profits and natural resource tax	Laan and Maino (2022)
Colombia	Oil-related	IMF Article IV report, March 2023, p.35
Congo	Oil	IMF Article IV report, October 2021, p.4
Ecuador	Oil	IMF Article IV report, July 2022, p.39
Egypt	Oil-related	IMF Article IV report, July 2021, p.34
Equatorial Guinea	Hydrocarbon	IMF Article IV report, July 2022, p.4
Gabon	Oil	IMF (2022: p.4)
Ghana	Oil	IMF Article IV report, July 2021, p.34
India	Oil and gas	Aggarwal et al. (2022)
Indonesia	Oil and gas	IMF Article IV report, June 2023, p.14
Iran	Oil	IMF Article IV report, March 2018, p.5
Iraq	Oil	IMF Article IV report, February 2023, p.16
Kazakhstan	Oil	IMF Article IV report, December 2022, p.5
Kuwait	Oil	IMF Article IV report, March 2022, p.26
Libya	Oil	IMF Article IV report, November 2022, p.49
Malaysia	Oil-related	IMF Article IV report, June 2023, p.12
Mexico	Oil	IMF Article IV report, February 2023, p.4
Nigeria	Oil and gas	IMF Article IV report, February 2023, p.4
Norway	Oil-related	IMF Article IV report, September 2022, p.30
Oman	Hydrocarbon	IMF Article IV report, November 2022, p.5
Qatar	Oil and LNG	IMF Article IV report, June 2022, pp.34-35
Russia	Oil	IMF Article IV report, February 2021, p.39
Saudi Arabia	Oil	IMF Article IV report, August 2022, p.20
South Sudan	Oil	IMF Article IV report, August 2022, p.5
Sudan	Oil	IMF Article IV report, March 2020, p.5
Timor-Leste	Oil	IMF Article IV report, September 2022, pp.30,37
Trinidad and Tobago	Energy	IMF Article IV report, May 2023, p.5
United Arab Emirates	Hydrocarbon	IMF Article IV report, June 2023, p.38
United Kingdom	Oil and gas	HM Revenue & Customs (2023: public sector finances tables)
United States	Federal oil and gas royalties	U.S. Department of the Interior (USDOI 2023)
Uzbekistan	Hydrocarbons	U.S. International Trade Administration (USITA 2021)
Venezuela	Oil	Armas (2022)

Table 1: Sources for oil and gas share of revenue

3 IMF Article IV reports are available at <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/SPROLLS/Article-iv-staff-reports> (IMF 2023). The page numbers in the table refer to the pdf document page number, rather than the marked page number.

COMBINING AND WEIGHTING THE ELEMENTS

The three elements are each normalized, to set the three elements on a comparable scale, and then combined as an average. For this analysis, following consultation with civil society partners in the report, we treat the three elements as equally important from a justice standpoint, although different weightings could be justified. A later online version of this framework will allow users more flexibility, including the ability to weight the elements according to their own judgements of their relative social importance.

SCALING ACCORDING TO CAPACITY TO OVERCOME DEPENDENCE

The three elements of dependence described above are in essence blind to the overall level of development of each country. To capture the self-evident fact that it is more difficult for a poor country to manage the transitional challenges of a rapid phaseout, we apply a scaling factor that reflects the country's capacity to overcome the challenges of dependence. This scaling factor is the ratio of the *discretionary income* – i.e. income beyond that required to lead a basic, healthy, dignified life – of a country's population to its total income (in this report, GDP is used as a proxy for income⁴).

To define a country's capacity explicitly, discretionary income is defined with respect to two thresholds, a USD 7,500⁵ per person per year ("basic development") threshold and a higher USD 50,000 threshold. No income below USD 7,500 (approximately \$20 per day) counts towards a country's capacity, as it is presumed to be required for meeting basic needs; all income above USD 50,000 does, as it is presumed to be essentially discretionary. For incomes between these two thresholds, a share that increases linearly from 0% to 100% is considered discretionary. (See box "Defining Capacity" below). All countries have some people living above the higher threshold and some living below the basic development threshold. The countries of the Global North have proportionately more people – and more of the country's total income – above the thresholds, though individual variations are significant. The civil society partners selected this way to define these thresholds, although other ways that are more progressive or less progressive could be defended as well. In a future online version of the equitable phaseout framework, users will be able to vary this definition. The definition used here is the same that the Civil Society Equity Review has used in its "High Progressivity" benchmark for assessing NDCs against fair shares of mitigation since its inception in 2015 (Civil Society Equity Review 2015).

The ratio of a country's discretionary income to its total income provides the basis for the capacity scaling factor. Since it is quite small for poor countries, and vanishingly small for very poor countries, a lower cutoff is applied to this ratio that corresponds to the 50% percentile across the full set of countries.

The average of the three elements of the composite measure of dependence is then divided by this capacity scaling factor, which serves as our measure of its economic adaptability or resilience. In other words, considering two countries with the same, unscaled, amount of dependence according to the three elements of the composite measure, the capacity-adjusted dependence indicator of the country with the higher capacity (i.e. larger fraction of discretionary income) will be lower than the other country, reflecting the fact that the higher-capacity country will find it relatively easier to overcome the same barriers to phaseout on account of its relatively more advantageous economic situation.

DIMENSIONS OF DEPENDENCE NOT INCLUDED

One dimension of employment dependence that has not yet been quantified in our framework (we aim to address it in future work) is the number of people relying on each job. In some countries, large households may depend on income

4 Conceptually, gross national income (GNI) would be the more appropriate measure to use here as a measure of capacity, since it includes income earned by a country's residents from sources outside the country while it does not include income earned in the country by non-residents. Instead, however, we are using GDP here as a proxy for GNI. The main reason is that publicly available data sets for GNI have major data gaps and are therefore not suited for an analysis like this that includes all countries. Importantly, GNI and GDP are extremely closely correlated (Pearson's correlation coefficient is 0.98), so that GDP is a suitable proxy for GNI, despite the former's relative weakness as a measure of capacity.

5 In 2005 United States Dollars, adjusted for purchasing power parity (PPP).

from a single earner; in others, significant numbers of unemployed workers may rely on social safety nets funded by well-paid fossil fuel jobs.

Other aspects of economic dependence on fossil fuel extraction include:

- The share of fossil fuels in overall economic activity or in added value;
- The share of fossil fuels in exports – a measure of a country's access to foreign currency, which is often needed for debt servicing;
- The share of capital stock that will be stranded in the transition;
- The lack of availability of alternative energy supplies or economic sectors;
- National macroeconomic, institutional and governance weaknesses.

In this report, rather than attempting to build a more complex indicator including these and other elements, we focus on the three core elements, which between them encompass the broad aspects of social and economic dependence. However, future iterations of our framework will consider alternative approaches to quantifying dependence that may capture other elements, and/or vary the weighting between elements.

FORMAL DESCRIPTION OF THE DEPENDENCE INDICATOR

The dependence indicator $d_{f,i}$ is defined, for each fuel f in each country i , as

$$d_{f,i} = [d_{E,f,i} + d_{R,f,i} + d_{J,f,i}] / \left(\frac{C_i}{GDP_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

... where each country i 's energy dependence $d_{E,f,i}$ for fuel f , based on extraction E , exports X and primary energy consumption K , is defined as

$$d_{E,f,i} = \frac{\alpha_E \cdot [E_{f,i} - X_{f,i}]}{K_i} \quad (2)$$

... and where α_E is a normalisation factor, as defined in equation (5) below.

Country i 's revenue dependence $d_{R,f,i}$ for fuel f is defined as the share of revenue $r_{f,i}$ associated with the extraction of fuel f of country i 's total government revenue r_i

$$d_{R,f,i} = \frac{\alpha_R \cdot r_{f,i}}{r_i} \quad (3)$$

Country i 's jobs dependence $d_{J,f,i}$ for fuel f is defined as workers $j_{f,i}$ employed in the extraction of fuel f as a fraction of country i 's total workforce W_i , across all economic sectors.

$$d_{J,f,i} = \frac{\alpha_J \cdot j_{f,i}}{W_i} \quad (4)$$

The normalisation factors α are defined such that $\alpha \times \Delta d_{lowest}$ is the same for each dependence element, where Δd_{lowest} is the difference between the lowest value and the mean value of that dependence element. Thus:

$$\alpha_E = \frac{\alpha_R \cdot \Delta d_{R,lowest}}{\Delta d_{E,lowest}} = \frac{\alpha_J \cdot \Delta d_{J,lowest}}{\Delta d_{E,lowest}} \quad (5)$$

Finally, GDP_i is country i 's gross domestic product, and C_i is its capacity, as defined in box 1 on page 16.

DEPENDENCE ASSESSMENT BY COUNTRY

Country	Fuel	Share of primary energy	Share of govt revenue	Share of jobs	GDP per capita	Capacity per capita	Dependence indicator
Algeria	Oil	34.84 %	17.80 %	1.73 %	\$ 4,532	\$ 88	6.08
Angola	Oil	26.48 %	60.09 %	1.18 %	\$ 2,815	\$ 16	8.74
Argentina	Oil	38.24 %	1.53 %	0.41 %	\$ 10,033	\$ 904	3.03
Australia	Oil	13.77 %	0.06 %	0.34 %	\$ 61,343	\$ 32,648	0.09
Azerbaijan	Oil	35.18 %	26.80 %	0.70 %	\$ 6,077	\$ 556	5.57
Brazil	Oil	37.34 %	3.99 %	0.35 %	\$ 11,197	\$ 2,339	1.74
Brunei	Oil	26.48 %	5.89 %	4.64 %	\$ 34,036	\$ 14,120	1.30
Canada	Oil	30.17 %	1.29 %	1.05 %	\$ 53,303	\$ 26,093	0.32
Chad	Oil	26.48 %	36.51 %	0.33 %	\$ 759	\$ 0	5.44
China	Oil	5.05 %	0.26 %	0.07 %	\$ 9,850	\$ 2,380	0.19
Colombia	Oil	43.82 %	1.41 %	0.36 %	\$ 8,630	\$ 1,527	2.32
Denmark	Oil	18.78 %	0.00 %	0.18 %	\$ 67,672	\$ 36,923	0.08
Ecuador	Oil	66.99 %	24.40 %	0.67 %	\$ 4,906	\$ 421	7.26
Egypt	Oil	30.17 %	0.67 %	0.29 %	\$ 3,330	\$ 38	2.31
Equatorial Guinea	Oil	26.48 %	80.39 %	3.11 %	\$ 7,653	\$ 526	13.17
Gabon	Oil	26.48 %	35.86 %	3.91 %	\$ 8,846	\$ 2,052	4.82
India	Oil	3.96 %	1.55 %	0.08 %	\$ 2,401	\$ 17	0.49
Indonesia	Oil	12.91 %	2.88 %	0.05 %	\$ 4,849	\$ 119	1.13
Iran	Oil	30.37 %	20.69 %	0.70 %	\$ 6,276	\$ 330	4.70
Iraq	Oil	69.03 %	84.73 %	2.13 %	\$ 5,631	\$ 216	14.89
Italy	Oil	2.95 %	0.00 %	0.03 %	\$ 36,120	\$ 12,708	0.05
Kazakhstan	Oil	24.94 %	24.41 %	0.97 %	\$ 11,884	\$ 1,544	5.07
Kuwait	Oil	50.47 %	54.27 %	6.59 %	\$ 31,865	\$ 11,822	3.45
Libya	Oil	26.48 %	77.59 %	6.98 %	\$ 15,911	\$ 3,011	11.52
Malaysia	Oil	22.97 %	5.04 %	0.37 %	\$ 12,889	\$ 1,988	1.99
Mexico	Oil	43.67 %	14.03 %	0.13 %	\$ 9,915	\$ 1,626	3.23
Nigeria	Oil	26.48 %	25.37 %	0.29 %	\$ 2,331	\$ 23	4.36
Norway	Oil	19.03 %	13.24 %	5.58 %	\$ 97,513	\$ 66,156	0.00
Oman	Oil	30.11 %	45.44 %	2.50 %	\$ 14,897	\$ 2,479	7.12
Peru	Oil	20.88 %	0.00 %	0.09 %	\$ 6,631	\$ 587	1.40
Qatar	Oil	29.59 %	22.20 %	4.65 %	\$ 61,334	\$ 36,258	0.37
Republic of Congo	Oil	26.48 %	33.07 %	1.68 %	\$ 1,998	\$ 11	6.91
Romania	Oil	9.88 %	0.00 %	0.07 %	\$ 13,285	\$ 1,788	0.70
Russian Federation	Oil	24.42 %	11.42 %	0.80 %	\$ 11,096	\$ 1,615	3.28
Saudi Arabia	Oil	62.20 %	49.21 %	4.01 %	\$ 21,393	\$ 5,596	5.39
South Sudan	Oil	26.48 %	86.13 %	0.48 %	\$ 588	\$ 0	10.23
Sudan	Oil	26.48 %	15.38 %	0.07 %	\$ 1,892	\$ 11	3.14
Syria	Oil	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.07 %	\$ 736	\$ 0	1.73
Thailand	Oil	12.81 %	0.00 %	0.09 %	\$ 6,635	\$ 429	0.91
Trinidad & Tobago	Oil	8.26 %	4.58 %	1.34 %	\$ 14,636	\$ 3,486	1.24
Tunisia	Oil	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.14 %	\$ 3,676	\$ 87	1.81
Turkmenistan	Oil	18.20 %	0.00 %	0.63 %	\$ 8,029	\$ 355	1.95
United Arab Emirates	Oil	43.29 %	41.77 %	3.22 %	\$ 41,351	\$ 19,106	1.25
United Kingdom	Oil	20.83 %	0.08 %	0.20 %	\$ 42,949	\$ 18,312	0.23
United States	Oil	36.31 %	0.11 %	0.42 %	\$ 58,664	\$ 34,684	0.10
Uzbekistan	Oil	5.84 %	0.59 %	0.02 %	\$ 2,817	\$ 34	0.44
Venezuela	Oil	24.07 %	36.34 %	0.83 %	\$ 3,418	\$ 54	5.94
Vietnam	Oil	8.27 %	0.00 %	0.04 %	\$ 2,419	\$ 15	0.56
Yemen	Oil	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.05 %	\$ 534	\$ 0	1.70

Table 2: Results of the dependence assessment for oil, for all countries in the analysis

Country	Fuel	Share of primary energy	Share of govt revenue	Share of jobs	GDP per capita	Capacity per capita	Dependence indicator
Algeria	Gas	64.65 %	21.78 %	212 %	\$ 4,532	\$ 88	8.80
Argentina	Gas	41.55 %	166 %	0.44 %	\$ 10,033	\$ 904	3.29
Australia	Gas	25.06 %	0.39 %	2.26 %	\$ 61,343	\$ 32,648	0.31
Azerbaijan	Gas	62.32 %	24.52 %	0.64 %	\$ 6,077	\$ 556	6.95
Bahrain	Gas	26.48 %	0.00 %	1.96 %	\$ 19,421	\$ 4,491	2.02
Bangladesh	Gas	46.67 %	0.00 %	0.07 %	\$ 1,513	\$ 2	2.96
Bolivia	Gas	26.48 %	14.34 %	0.52 %	\$ 2,573	\$ 164	3.64
Brazil	Gas	6.17 %	0.54 %	0.05 %	\$ 11,197	\$ 2,339	0.27
Brunei	Gas	26.48 %	12.48 %	9.82 %	\$ 34,036	\$ 14,120	2.48
Canada	Gas	30.96 %	0.79 %	0.64 %	\$ 53,303	\$ 26,093	0.27
China	Gas	5.01 %	0.25 %	0.07 %	\$ 9,850	\$ 2,380	0.19
Colombia	Gas	20.40 %	0.43 %	0.11 %	\$ 8,630	\$ 1,527	1.01
Denmark	Gas	7.72 %	0.00 %	0.08 %	\$ 67,672	\$ 36,923	0.03
Egypt	Gas	54.95 %	1.29 %	0.57 %	\$ 3,330	\$ 38	4.25
Germany	Gas	1.25 %	0.00 %	0.02 %	\$ 48,271	\$ 21,590	0.01
India	Gas	2.94 %	1.15 %	0.06 %	\$ 2,401	\$ 17	0.36
Indonesia	Gas	13.63 %	4.75 %	0.09 %	\$ 4,849	\$ 119	1.39
Iran	Gas	67.79 %	25.80 %	0.87 %	\$ 6,276	\$ 330	7.71
Iraq	Gas	14.72 %	3.25 %	0.08 %	\$ 5,631	\$ 216	1.31
Italy	Gas	1.85 %	0.00 %	0.02 %	\$ 36,120	\$ 12,708	0.03
Kazakhstan	Gas	25.04 %	6.58 %	0.26 %	\$ 11,884	\$ 1,544	2.49
Kuwait	Gas	30.11 %	4.40 %	0.53 %	\$ 31,865	\$ 11,822	0.61
Libya	Gas	26.48 %	19.41 %	1.75 %	\$ 15,911	\$ 3,011	3.66
Malaysia	Gas	36.76 %	13.47 %	0.99 %	\$ 12,889	\$ 1,988	4.05
Mexico	Gas	16.65 %	5.35 %	0.05 %	\$ 9,915	\$ 1,626	1.23
Myanmar	Gas	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.15 %	\$ 1,241	\$ 2	1.82
Netherlands	Gas	15.32 %	0.00 %	0.24 %	\$ 58,068	\$ 29,901	0.10
Nigeria	Gas	26.48 %	12.98 %	0.15 %	\$ 2,331	\$ 23	3.03
Norway	Gas	7.57 %	15.72 %	6.63 %	\$ 97,513	\$ 66,156	0.00
Oman	Gas	68.66 %	33.02 %	1.81 %	\$ 14,897	\$ 2,479	7.37
Pakistan	Gas	28.67 %	0.00 %	0.08 %	\$ 1,262	\$ 0	1.87
Peru	Gas	28.73 %	0.00 %	0.17 %	\$ 6,631	\$ 587	2.00
Poland	Gas	3.34 %	0.00 %	0.03 %	\$ 19,238	\$ 3,927	0.14
Qatar	Gas	70.10 %	29.40 %	8.61 %	\$ 61,334	\$ 36,258	0.67
Romania	Gas	24.48 %	0.00 %	0.17 %	\$ 13,285	\$ 1,788	1.73
Russian Federation	Gas	50.84 %	11.58 %	0.82 %	\$ 11,096	\$ 1,615	4.78
Saudi Arabia	Gas	37.69 %	8.97 %	0.73 %	\$ 21,393	\$ 5,596	1.62
Syria	Gas	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.04 %	\$ 736	\$ 0	1.69
Thailand	Gas	18.23 %	0.00 %	0.13 %	\$ 6,635	\$ 429	1.30
Trinidad & Tobago	Gas	91.73 %	29.63 %	8.69 %	\$ 14,636	\$ 3,486	9.08
Turkmenistan	Gas	81.79 %	0.00 %	3.70 %	\$ 8,029	\$ 355	9.92
United States	Gas	33.08 %	0.11 %	0.43 %	\$ 58,664	\$ 34,684	0.10
Ukraine	Gas	27.04 %	0.00 %	0.14 %	\$ 1,834	\$ 9	1.85
United Arab Emirates	Gas	41.35 %	11.07 %	0.85 %	\$ 41,351	\$ 19,106	0.54
United Kingdom	Gas	18.78 %	0.07 %	0.18 %	\$ 42,949	\$ 18,312	0.20
Uzbekistan	Gas	82.42 %	8.41 %	0.34 %	\$ 2,817	\$ 34	6.30
Venezuela	Gas	47.55 %	26.66 %	0.61 %	\$ 3,418	\$ 54	6.20
Vietnam	Gas	6.12 %	0.00 %	0.03 %	\$ 2,419	\$ 15	0.42
Yemen	Gas	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 534	\$ 0	1.63

Table 3: Results of the dependence assessment for gas, for all countries in the analysis

Country	Fuel	Share of primary energy	Share of govt revenue	Share of jobs	GDP per capita	Capacity per capita	Dependence indicator
Australia	Coal	25.93 %	0.00 %	2.34 %	\$ 61,343	\$ 32,648	0.32
Brazil	Coal	0.80 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 11,197	\$ 2,339	0.03
Bulgaria	Coal	29.72 %	0.00 %	0.15 %	\$ 10,018	\$ 784	2.03
Canada	Coal	2.73 %	0.00 %	0.04 %	\$ 53,303	\$ 26,093	0.02
China	Coal	55.47 %	0.00 %	0.43 %	\$ 9,850	\$ 2,380	1.78
Colombia	Coal	4.68 %	0.00 %	0.18 %	\$ 8,630	\$ 1,527	0.37
Czech Republic	Coal	28.83 %	0.00 %	0.17 %	\$ 25,033	\$ 5,618	1.00
Germany	Coal	9.84 %	0.00 %	0.05 %	\$ 48,271	\$ 21,590	0.09
Greece	Coal	6.00 %	0.00 %	0.03 %	\$ 25,920	\$ 6,723	0.16
Hungary	Coal	3.34 %	0.00 %	0.01 %	\$ 19,633	\$ 3,254	0.17
India	Coal	41.21 %	0.00 %	0.27 %	\$ 2,401	\$ 17	2.89
Indonesia	Coal	44.81 %	0.00 %	0.29 %	\$ 4,849	\$ 119	3.15
Japan	Coal	0.09 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 50,291	\$ 23,525	0.00
Kazakhstan	Coal	45.98 %	0.00 %	0.50 %	\$ 11,884	\$ 1,544	3.49
Mexico	Coal	1.58 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 9,915	\$ 1,626	0.08
Mongolia	Coal	26.48 %	0.00 %	1.58 %	\$ 4,295	\$ 56	3.72
New Zealand	Coal	5.46 %	0.00 %	0.06 %	\$ 43,514	\$ 18,457	0.06
Pakistan	Coal	5.18 %	0.00 %	0.01 %	\$ 1,262	\$ 0	0.33
Poland	Coal	39.50 %	0.00 %	0.17 %	\$ 19,238	\$ 3,927	1.53
Romania	Coal	9.93 %	0.00 %	0.03 %	\$ 13,285	\$ 1,788	0.65
Russian Federation	Coal	11.06 %	0.00 %	0.34 %	\$ 11,096	\$ 1,615	1.02
Serbia	Coal	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.15 %	\$ 6,682	\$ 305	1.82
South Africa	Coal	68.75 %	0.00 %	0.81 %	\$ 7,063	\$ 1,009	4.91
South Korea	Coal	0.13 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 31,406	\$ 10,547	0.00
Spain	Coal	0.03 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 34,189	\$ 11,485	0.00
Thailand	Coal	2.79 %	0.00 %	0.01 %	\$ 6,635	\$ 429	0.19
Turkiye	Coal	11.88 %	0.00 %	0.05 %	\$ 17,545	\$ 4,252	0.35
Ukraine	Coal	15.50 %	0.00 %	0.03 %	\$ 1,834	\$ 9	1.00
United Kingdom	Coal	0.25 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 42,949	\$ 18,312	0.00
United States	Coal	10.29 %	0.00 %	0.05 %	\$ 58,664	\$ 34,684	0.03
Uzbekistan	Coal	3.01 %	0.00 %	0.01 %	\$ 2,817	\$ 34	0.20
Venezuela	Coal	0.07 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	\$ 3,418	\$ 54	0.01
Vietnam	Coal	25.46 %	0.00 %	0.06 %	\$ 2,419	\$ 15	1.65
Zimbabwe	Coal	26.48 %	0.00 %	0.06%	\$ 1,145	\$ 92	1.71

Table 4: Results of the dependence assessment for coal, for all countries in the analysis

NATIONAL FOSSIL FUEL PRODUCTION PHASEOUT PATHWAYS

Our objective is to define fossil fuel production phaseout pathways for all producing countries,⁶ in a manner that requires less dependent countries to phase out more rapidly, and more dependent countries to phase out less rapidly. Still, because of the starkly limited remaining carbon budget, global fossil fuel production must decline extraordinarily rapidly if the world is to limit warming to 1.5 °C.

THE 1.5 °C EMISSIONS PATHWAY

We define the 1.5 °C guardrail with reference to the Low Energy Demand (LED) Pathway (Grübler et al. 2018), which was one of the four illustrative 1.5 °C pathways presented in the IPCC's 1.5 °C Report (IPCC 2018) and revised as one of the five illustrative mitigation pathways for the IPCC 6th Assessment Report (IPCC 2022; Byers et al. 2022). We take from this pathway the cumulative global total for carbon dioxide emissions from fossil fuels, thus setting the overall pace of the global fossil fuel decline. This pathway is classified as a 1.5 °C pathway by the IPCC, and takes a precautionary approach to unproven technologies, so does not rely at all on technological Carbon Dioxide Removal or carbon capture and storage.⁷ In total, it allows approximately 440 GtCO₂ of post-2020 fossil fuel carbon dioxide emissions.

Still, even this ambitious emissions pathway presents considerable risks. Even though it is one of the lower overshoot pathways summarized by the IPCC, the LED Pathway still has a 62% risk of peaking above 1.5 °C, and a 33% risk of peaking above 1.71 °C. Moreover, in 2100, it still has a 24% risk of exceeding 1.5 °C, and a 12% risk of exceeding even 2 °C. Thus, given the climate impacts already being experienced at the current temperature rise of ~1.2 °C, it cannot be understood as "safe" or free from "dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system" (UNFCCC 1992, Article 2).

Additionally, the LED pathway presupposes extremely ambitious mitigation of the non-CO₂ GHG emissions, rapid elimination of deforestation emissions, and the availability of approximately 200 GtCO₂ worth of land-based carbon dioxide sequestration (afforestation/reforestation). This would likely imply an additional demand on land that would need to be met without compromising food security, biodiversity, freshwater resources, livelihoods or indigenous peoples' rights, which raises further constraints and challenges. To assume the availability of even more negative emissions (as many mitigation scenarios do) would escalate the associated challenges and require accepting even greater risks.

HOW WE CHARACTERIZE NATIONAL FOSSIL FUEL PHASEOUT PATHWAYS

Given this 1.5 °C-consistent cumulative total for fossil fuel emissions, we then define phaseout paths for fossil fuel producing countries in accordance with their relative dependence on extraction, as defined above (in the Dependence Indicator section). This is a simplification of an actual transition pathway, of course, which in reality would be driven by numerous social, technical, economic, and political factors. While energy system models focus primarily on the techno-economic factors, here we focus primarily on the social factors, and specifically on dependence.

Since it takes time to change consumption patterns, to build clean sources of energy etc., we can expect a pathway that starts flat and then declines at an increasing annual rate over time. We choose to represent each country's overall

6 We include in our analysis all countries included in the Energy Institute's Statistical Review of World Energy 2023 (Energy Institute 2023a), which includes the 34 producers of coal (98.6% of global oil production), 49 producers of gas (97.9% of global gas production), and 49 producers of oil (98.6% of global oil production) shown in the accompanying tables.

7 This lack of reliance on unproven technologies makes it more ambitious than most other global pathways for fossil fuel phaseouts, and place it beyond what is considered politically realistic in conventional policy discourse.

extraction decline pathway (for each fuel) as a Gaussian curve, also known as a normal curve or bell curve. While there are other S-curve functions we could have used, the precise choice would not significantly change the results. We choose the Gaussian because it provides a straightforward and mathematically convenient expression. Then, for any fuel f and country i , the extraction pathway over time is expressed in the form

$$E_{f,i}(t) = E_0 \cdot e^{-\beta_{f,i} \cdot t^2} \quad (6)$$

where t is time since the initial year (which is 2023 in our analysis), E_0 is the extraction rate in the initial year for a given country and fuel, and the parameter β determines the speed of the overall transition and decline. Throughout the report, we use the term “phaseout year” to refer to the year by which a country’s extraction would have been essentially phased out, that is, diminished to less than 10% of its 2023 extraction level (i.e. at least a 90% reduction below present level, reflected by the 0.1 in equation (7)). By simple substitution, it follows that this nominal phaseout year is given by

$$t_{PHASEOUT,f,i} = \sqrt{\frac{-\ln(0.1)}{\beta_{f,i}}} \quad (7)$$

By integrating the Gaussian formula, it further follows that the total extraction over time, E_{CUM} , for any fuel f and country i , is

$$E_{CUM,f,i} = \frac{E_0}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\beta_{f,i}}} \quad (8)$$

CALCULATING NATIONAL PHASEOUT PATHWAYS ACCORDING TO DEPENDENCE ON PRODUCTION

We now wish to assign a set of decline rates, $\beta_{f,i}$, for each country i and fuel f , such that the lower a country’s dependence on extraction of a particular fuel, the more rapid its decline pathway than the global average, and vice versa. In order to express oil, gas, and coal in the same units and ensure that their combined total is consistent with our selected 1.5 °C pathway, we express the amount of fossil fuels extracted in terms of the carbon dioxide emissions that the combustion of the fuels would emit. We thus require that the aggregate cumulative extraction across all countries and fuels (or rather: the cumulative emissions resulting from the combustion of the aggregate cumulative extraction) must sum to the LED pathway’s total cumulative carbon dioxide emissions from fossil fuels, $E_{CUM,LED}$.

We first define a global average decline parameter, $\bar{\beta}$, determined by the total fossil fuel extraction volume corresponding to the cumulative carbon dioxide emissions from fossil fuels under the LED pathway, $E_{CUM,LED}$, and the initial extraction rate $E_{0,LED}$, as

$$\bar{\beta} = \frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{E_{0,LED}}{E_{CUM,LED}} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

and a global extraction-weighted average dependence indicator, \bar{d} , as

$$\bar{d} = \frac{1}{E_0} \sum_{f,i} d_{i,f} E_{0,f,i} \quad (10)$$

Then, for any given country i and fuel f , a decline rate can be defined as

$$\beta_{f,i} = \frac{1}{\left(\alpha \Delta d_{f,i} + 1/\sqrt{\bar{\beta}} \right)^2} \quad (11)$$

where $\Delta d_{i,f}$ is the difference between a given country's dependence and the global mean dependence

$$\Delta d_{f,i} = d_{f,i} - \bar{d} \tag{12}$$

The parameter α sets the scale of the impact of the dependence factor on all countries' phaseout rates. If α were set to zero, then a country's dependence would have no impact on its phaseout rate, meaning all countries would have the same phaseout rate. The choice of this scaling factor α thus has normative implications, as it entails a trade-off among practical, political, and ethical concerns. For this analysis, our civil society partners considered the tensions between, on the one hand, the urgency of the climate problem and, on the other, the practical and political obstacles to extremely rapid phaseout and the magnitude of the phaseout challenges facing the most dependent countries. Based on their ethical position with regards to these considerations, they decided that the scaling factor α should be set such that the least dependent countries will have phaseout dates no earlier than 2030.⁸ Note, even a phaseout date this soon for the least dependent countries, some of which are major global producers, will still require phaseout dates for more dependent countries that imply major practical challenges, especially for the least wealthy of them.

Figures 1-3 show the phaseout dates calculated for each country and each fuel (x-axis), along with that country's composite (energy, employment, and revenue) dependence (y-axis). One consequence of this approach is that each country's phaseout period lengthens in proportion to its dependence indicator. That is, having set 2030 as the earliest phaseout year, a country with twice the dependence of another would be allocated twice as many years after this date to phase out extraction. In a handful of cases (Iraq, Equatorial Guinea, Libya and South Sudan for oil, and Turkmenistan for gas), our algorithm yielded phaseout years after 2050. Based on the broad consensus of the global climate movement that fossil fuel extraction ought to cease worldwide by 2050, the Civil Society Equity Review partners decided to cap the phaseout date to 2050. For the five cases mentioned, figures 1 and 2 therefore show both the uncapped phaseout year as well as the adjusted figure that is reported in the main report results.

Figure 1: National Extraction Phaseout Years for Oil and Dependence on Oil Extraction.

8 This was obtained with a scaling factor of $\alpha = 1.32$.

The resulting total global production pathways for coal, oil, and gas are displayed in the following graphs, showing both the phaseout pathways as we calculate them, and the fuel-specific pathways resulting from the original LED analysis. Note that the passage of time (2020-2023) has already resulted in a significant overshoot of production in the real world compared to that assumed in the LED modelling analysis, which of course means that subsequent production must decline even more rapidly than in the LED pathway.

Figure 4: Aggregate global emissions pathways (CO₂) for each fuel type (oil – panel a, coal – panel b, gas – panel c) for the LED pathway (orange line) and the aggregate national allocations of extraction in this study (blue line).

Note also that the aggregate production of coal declines the fastest of the three fuels, as in the LED Pathway, even though we do not impose this consistency as a fixed requirement. Rather, it is because dependence on coal production tends to be significantly lower than dependence on extraction of oil and gas. As a result, the phaseout timeframes for coal are shorter than for gas and oil.

This is of course not wholly coincidental. The fact that coal declines faster in the LED pathway is linked to the fact that though it is less costly per unit of energy, it is not as versatile and valuable as gas and oil, which serve as suitable substitutes. Relatedly, producing the higher value oil and gas implies more jobs and generates more public revenue, and hence is linked to greater national dependence as defined here.

CALCULATING INTERNATIONAL SUPPORT FOR FOSSIL FUEL EXTRACTION PHASEOUT

The present report conceptualizes equity in fossil-fuel extraction phaseout not merely by calculating nationally differentiated phase-out dates. It also provides a lower bound of the international financial support that lower-capacity countries will need to receive to achieve the accelerated phase-out dates that are now necessary, and it details how the provision of that support should be shared fairly by the high-capacity countries. This is an important innovation of this report.

This fossil-fuel extraction phaseout framework would be incomplete, and thus unjust, if it neglected support. This is because the phaseout must, at this point, happen so quickly, in all fossil-fuel-extracting countries, that differentiated phase-out timelines alone cannot reflect any defensibly equitable phase-out plan. Even if it defined the most aggressive conceivable phase-out timelines for the least-dependent countries and the most lenient timelines for the most-dependent countries, those timelines could not in themselves be equitable if they were also compliant in aggregate with a global 1.5°C-consistent phase-out trajectory. More precisely, phaseout timelines, in the absence of support, would be unfairly aggressive, particularly for the most-dependent countries. In our assessment, this challenge can only be met by ensuring that highly-dependent fossil-fuel-extracting countries, which are now being asked to phase out their extraction on an accelerated timeline, are given the appropriate amount of support to lessen the structural injustice this situation presents for them.

CONCEPTUAL OVERVIEW OF THE APPROACH FOR FOSSIL-FUEL EXTRACTION PHASEOUT SUPPORT PROVISION AND RECEIPT

		Current fossil fuel extractor	
		Yes	No
Per capita capacity	Above average	I fully finance own phase out; provide support for III	II provide support for III
	Below average	III partially finance own phase out, receive support for remainder	IV no role in phasing out fossil fuel extraction

Figure 5: Typology of countries by status as current fossil fuel extractor and per capita capacity relative to global average.

Conceptually, our approach for calculating the scale of the fossil-fuel-extraction phaseout support needed begins by organizing countries based on two factors – their level of capacity (see box) and whether they currently extract fossil fuels, as depicted in Figure 5 above.

In our support framework, all countries with a per-capita capacity above the global average (groups I+II) have to contribute to the global fossil-fuel extraction phaseout by providing financial support to those extractors who require it (III). If high-capacity countries are also current fossil fuel extractors (I), they need to provide this support in addition to financing their own extraction phaseout. If they are not current extractors (II), their only role within this framework is the provision of support.

Countries with a per-capita capacity below the global average, if they are current fossil-fuel extractors (III), would partially fund their own fossil-fuel extraction phaseout, to the degree consistent with their fair share of such a phase-out effort. However, countries with below-global-average per capita capacity who are not current fossil fuel extractors (IV) are not included in this framework as recipients of fossil-fuel-extraction phase-out support (because they have no phase-out effort to support), nor are they considered to have fair share obligations to countries in category III. For example, Tuvalu would not be expected to help fund the extraction phaseout in Iraq and Nigeria.

Box 1: Defining Capacity

This equitable fossil-fuel extraction phaseout equity framework uses the same notion of “capacity” that has been used in the Civil Society Equity Review since its inception in 2015, based on the Climate Equity Reference Framework (Baer et al. 2008, 2009; Holz et al. 2018). Within this Framework, a country’s capacity is conceptualized as the fraction of the country’s GDP⁹ that need not be prioritized for meeting the basic essentials needed for a dignified life for all of the country’s population, instead of climate action. This exclusion is operationalized by taking account of the country’s internal income distribution. In practice, this is done by defining a lower threshold (the “development threshold”) below which incomes are fully exempt from being considered part of a country’s capacity that can be mobilized for climate action. In the Civil Society Equity Review (2015), this level is set to \$7,500 per person per year (in 2005 USD,¹⁰ adjusted for purchasing power parity (PPP)) – a level that has been found to roughly equate to the decent living standard at which the intergenerational impacts of extreme poverty start to dissipate (Pritchett 2003, 2006). Thus, only the portion of a country’s GDP that corresponds to incomes above this threshold is counted as a country’s capacity, thus lowering the capacity (relative to GDP) for countries with large populations living in poverty.

Additionally, we treat incomes just above the development threshold differently than the incomes of much wealthier individuals, similarly to the approach followed by “progressive” income tax systems (where tax rates “progress,” or increase, along with increases in income). Therefore, in its “High Progressivity” equity benchmark, the Civil Society Equity Review uses a second higher threshold, set at \$50,000 per person per year (in 2010 USD, without PPP adjustment). Only incomes above this higher threshold are *fully* counted as contributing to a country’s capacity to respond to the climate crisis (as any additional income above this higher threshold is thought to correspond to discretionary consumption), while the degree to which incomes between the lower and upper thresholds are counted as capacity gradually increases between the thresholds. This reflects the notion that incomes just above the development threshold mostly still represent non-discretionary spending, but that this changes as incomes increase further above the lower threshold.

The choice of these two thresholds corresponds to the Civil Society Equity Review’s “High Progressivity” definition of capacity. Additionally, each country is deemed a higher-capacity or lower-capacity country based on whether its average per-capita capacity is higher or lower than the global average.

Conceptually, our framework differentiates the total global fossil-fuel phase-out cost into three segments, as depicted in Figure 6 below.

- Total phaseout costs, P_1 , that will be incurred in type I countries, i.e. high-capacity fossil fuel extractors, is entirely born by these countries themselves. Intuitively, this can be justified by the fact that high-capacity countries, by virtue of being high-capacity countries, possess the resources necessary to cover their own phase-out costs. Additionally, and more importantly, in the effort-sharing framework utilized here, these countries’ aggregate fair

9 Regarding our choice of GDP over GNI see footnote 4.

10 We use 2005 PPP USD because global datasets with conversion factors to PPP are updated very infrequently, and 2005 data are readily available.

share of global extraction phase-out costs far exceeds the costs incurred by their own economies for their extraction phaseouts, even though these may be large (note, in Table 5, that the figure for their own aggregate phase-out costs here is roughly \$100bn (panel a), while their aggregate fair share is much larger at roughly \$300bn (panel b)). Thus, they are expected to cover not only their own costs, but also a fraction of other country's costs. Similarly, type II countries, by virtue of not having fossil fuel extraction to phase out, have zero phase-out costs of their own, but – since they are high-capacity countries – have a substantial fair share of the global phase-out costs – approximately \$40bn (panel b).

- The phase-out costs, P_{III} , that will be incurred in type III countries, i.e. lower-capacity fossil fuel extractors, is further differentiated into a portion that these countries are required to bear with their own resources as their fair share (F_{III}) and that which they cannot be expected to bear themselves, and should therefore be entitled to receive support for ($S_{REC,III}$). In the present analysis the figure used for P_{III} is roughly \$310bn (Table 5, panel a), while F_{III} is roughly \$70bn (panel b), from which follows that $S_{REC,III}$ is approximately \$240bn.
- $S_{REC,III}$, then, being part of the total phase-out costs that are incurred in type III countries (because they relate to the extraction phaseout occurring there) but achieved with international support, are thus born collectively by type I & II countries since they exceed type III countries' fair share. For this reason, they are matched by support to be provided by type I and II countries, $S_{PROV,I+II}$, as depicted in Figure 6.

a. Aggregate phase-out cost (USD bn)		b. Aggregate Fair Shares of Global Costs (USD bn)		c. Aggregate Responsibility-Capacity-Index:		d. Fossil Fuel Extraction Jobs (million jobs)	
Type I 108.0	Type II 0.0	Type I 309.7	Type II 38.4	Type I 73.7%	Type II 9.2%	Type I 4.7	Type II 0.0
Type III 312.0	Type IV 0.0	Type III 70.2	Type IV¹¹ 1.7	Type III 16.7%	Type IV 0.4%	Type III 13.6	Type IV 0.0

Table 5: Key metrics of approximate aggregate costs by country typology

In its fair-share calculations, the Civil Society Equity Review has always maintained that every single country in the world has a fair share of the global effort to address climate change, in accordance with its capacity and/or responsibility. These fair shares may, for low-capacity and/or low-responsibility countries, be very small, but they are never zero. Thus, in this fossil fuel extraction phaseout equity framework, each fossil fuel extracting country, even those with low capacity and high dependence have a non-zero share of the global phaseout effort (in the current context expressed as cost). This is what area F_{III} refers to: the aggregate *fair shares* (see Box 2 “Defining Fair Shares”) of all fossil fuel extracting countries with per capita capacity below global average (i.e., type III countries). The key point here is that, in aggregate, these countries' total extraction phaseout costs are *higher* than their fair share (by amount $S_{REC,III}$), which suggest that while those additional costs have to be incurred within their economies, they cannot be fairly expected to bear the burden of these costs, which, in turn, means that they ought to be eligible for and receive support and/or finance at a scale equivalent to this excess costs (area $S_{REC,III}$). In this extraction phaseout equity framework, these excess costs are appropriately born by the higher-than-average-capacity countries of type I and type II, thus requiring aggregate support and/or finance of this same scale ($S_{PROV,I+II}$)

11 Type IV countries' theoretical fair share of the global phase-out costs would be \$1.7 billion if these costs were shared purely based on countries' shares of the global capacity and responsibility. However, as mentioned earlier, type III and IV countries are not expected to contribute to provision of phase-out support because their per-capita capacity is below the global average, even though their theoretical fair share exceeds their own phase-out costs (because they are, by definition, zero – panel a).

Figure 6: Conceptual differentiation between supported and unsupported portions of the global fossil fuel extraction phase-out costs

The aggregate quantity of support and/or finance that needs to flow from type I + II countries to type III countries, is then shared among individual type I and type II countries according to their share of the aggregate responsibility and capacity of all type I and II countries (see Box 2 “Defining Fair Shares”). Those are the support fractions and dollar amounts reported in the first two columns of table ES-1 and in table 1 in the Report.

Box 2: Defining Fair Shares

The present analysis calculates “fair share” using the same effort sharing methodology that the Civil Society Equity Review has been utilizing since its inception in 2015, namely, the Climate Equity Reference Framework (Holz et al. 2018; Civil Society Equity Review 2015; Baer et al. 2008). At the core of the Climate Equity Reference Framework is the Responsibility-Capacity Index, RCI, which combines (in the present analysis with equal weighting), for each country, the country’s fraction of the aggregate global responsibility and capacity, while taking into account the unavoidable fact that basic development needs (i.e. eradication of poverty and ensuring decent standard of living for all) cannot be set aside just because ambitious climate action is now needed.

While prior reports of the Civil Society Equity Review utilize two different versions of the RCI (reflecting different perspectives of fairness in international effort-sharing), the present analysis, for simplicity, uses only a single operationalization of the RCI. Owing to a normative preference for higher progressivity, the civil society partners elected to use the “1850–High Progressivity” benchmark here (Civil Society Equity Review 2015), wherein capacity is defined as explained in Box 1 “Defining Capacity” and responsibility refers to the cumulative emissions of a country from 1850 to, in this case, 2023 (excluding “survival” emissions¹² associated with the subsistence consumption of the poorest). Note that in this extraction equity framework, responsibility is defined in the same way as in mitigation fair

12 Survival emissions are defined here in relation to the “development threshold” explained above in the context of measuring capacity (see box 1) – “survival emissions” are those emissions associated with consumption below the development threshold. The philosophical justification for treating survival (or “subsistence”) emissions differently from “luxury” emissions has a long history in the scholarly literature on climate justice – see, for example, Shue (1993).

shares, in relation to historic territorial emissions, not in relation to historic extraction. Whereas territorial emissions are strongly correlated with developmental status, and hence countries can be seen to have benefited from historic emissions, the relationship of extraction with development is more complex (for example, often a multinational corporation may take a disproportionate share of the profits), hence there is a weaker moral case for assigning responsibility to the country where extraction occurred (Muttitt and Kartha 2020).

In the present analysis, fair shares calculations via the RCI are used in two ways: First, to calculate, for type III countries, their aggregate fair share of the global fossil fuel extraction phase-out costs, i.e. the amount of effort they can fairly be expected to contribute to the global fossil fuel extraction phase-out. This is then contrasted to the fossil fuel extraction phase-out costs expected within these countries to generate indicative figures for their collective support need. Second, to calculate the fair shares of each individual type I and II country of the provision of phase-out support to type III countries.

THE ALGORITHM FOR CALCULATING FOSSIL FUEL EXTRACTION PHASEOUT SUPPORT PROVISION

Having described the conceptual framework, the following section will describe the algorithm used to calculate: 1. the global aggregate fossil fuel extraction phase-out costs, 2. the aggregate fraction of the phase-out cost that incur in type I and type III countries, respectively, 3. the aggregate fair share of the global fossil fuel extraction phase-out costs that belong to type I, II, and III countries, respectively, 4. the aggregate amount that should be provided as international phase-out support to type III countries, and 5. the individual shares of this support that should be provided by individual type I and type II countries.

It is important to note that, except for the last step, all calculations are carried out on the level of aggregates of large numbers of countries, as opposed to individual countries. This is because phase-out costs data for individual countries are not generally available, and because we do not consider any of the potential approaches to disaggregate from global figures to country-level resolution sufficiently robust. However, we do consider disaggregation of global figures into two large groups of countries adequate for providing indicative results.

1. The global fossil fuel extraction phase-out cost P is defined as the sum of the individual phase-out costs p_i of all type I and III countries (alternatively, it can also be understood as the sum of the phase-out costs of all countries, but since these costs are, by definition, zero for type II and IV, there is no practical difference).

$$P = \sum_i p_i \quad (13)$$

Ideally, P would be calculated as the sum of all p_i , but information of sufficient quality on individual countries' phase-out costs is not broadly available. Therefore, we derive an indicative lower bound for P based on data from the literature. More work is needed on country level needs-based assessment of phase-out-related costs, at which time the indicative figure used here should be replaced by the aggregate of those individual figures.

In the present report, based on the literature (see section "The Scale of Support," pp. 22-24, especially Box 3 in the main report), the figure used for P is USD \$420 billion for the total annual global phase-out cost and investment need (the lower end of the \$420bn to \$4.1tn range based on literature review).

2. The global phase-out cost P is then split into the costs for the type I and type III groups. For this analysis, we make the highly simplifying assumption that each group's phase-out costs are proportional to the jobs in its fossil fuel sectors, J_I and J_{III} , as a fraction of the total global fossil fuel extraction workforce, J .

$$P_I = P \times \frac{J_I}{J} ; P_{III} = P \times \frac{J_{III}}{J} \quad (14)$$

Note, Type II and Type IV countries are not fossil fuel producers, so their costs are zero.

3. To calculate fossil-fuel extracting countries' fair shares of the global phase-out costs, we adopt as a metric of fair effort sharing, the Responsibility-Capacity Index (RCI) as defined by the Climate Equity Reference Framework (Kemp-Benedict et al. 2018; Holz et al. 2019, 2018). For this analysis, we parameterize the RCI using the "1850-High Progressivity" set of normative choices, as in previous fair share analyses of the Civil Society Equity Review (e.g., Civil Society Equity Review 2015).

The $RCI_{i,t}$ for each of the countries i , is defined as the average of country i 's share $R_{i,t}$ of the total global responsibility and country i 's share $C_{i,t}$ of the total global capacity in the year t . In the present analysis, RCIs for the year 2023 are used, thus t is constant at 2023 and is therefore omitted from subsequent equations. (Other choices for y are also plausible, for example one could also choose to calculating support need and provision for each year using that same year's RCIs.)

$$RCI_i = \left(\frac{R_i}{\sum_j R_j} + \frac{C_i}{\sum_j C_j} \right) / 2 \quad (15)$$

Where R_i is the cumulative historic territorial greenhouse gas emissions of country i from a start year (here: 1850) to and end year (here: 2023), and C_i is country i 's capacity, as defined in Box 1.

Since our algorithm utilizes aggregates by country type, the aggregate RCIs for each group (type I – IV) of countries are calculated.

$$RCI_I = \sum_i RCI_i \quad (16)$$

$$RCI_{II} = \sum_j RCI_j \quad (17)$$

etc.

4. Since type III countries should receive support for the fraction of their aggregate fossil fuel extraction phase-out costs that exceed their fair share of the global phase-out costs we first calculate their aggregate fair share F_{III} of the global phase-out costs P , by multiplying their aggregate RCI, RCI_{III} , with the global phase-out costs P .

$$F_{III} = P \times RCI_{III} \quad (18)$$

Recalling the conceptual disaggregation of the global phase-out costs, this is area F_{III} in Figure 6.

For type III countries, we can now calculate the aggregate amount of international support they should receive to facilitate their accelerated fossil fuel extraction phaseouts, $S_{REC,III}$, by subtracting their aggregate fair share F_{III} of global costs from the aggregate phase-out costs incurring in type III countries P_{III} .

$$S_{REC,III} = P_{III} - F_{III} \quad (19)$$

Note that, if the aggregate fair share F of the global fossil fuel extraction phase-out costs for a group of countries were larger than the aggregate fraction of the global costs P incurred by that group, this group would not be eligible to receive support since S_{REC} would be negative.

In the present analysis, this is the case for type I countries, but is not the case for type III countries.

In Principle, if robust individual country-level data were available, this calculation could be performed on a country-level basis instead of large aggregates of countries, and $S_{REC,i}$ could be used to define whether countries are eligible support recipients (for $S_{REC,i} > 0$) or should, instead, contribute to the provision of support (for $S_{REC,i} < 0$).

5. Having thus defined the aggregate amount of support $S_{REC,III}$ that type III countries are eligible to receive, we have also defined the aggregate amount to be provided collectively by type I and II countries, $S_{PROV,I+II}$. (hence, areas $S_{REC,III}$ and $S_{PROV,I+II}$ in Figure 6 are shown as being of identical size)

$$S_{PROV,I+II} = S_{REC,III} \quad (20)$$

The sharing of the aggregate support among the individual type I and II countries is once again done using their Responsibility-Capacity Index as defined above (15). Thus, for each type I and type II country i , the country's share of the total aggregate support to be provided by type I and II countries, $S_{PROV,I+II}$, is proportional to the fraction of that country's RCI_i of the total of the RCI of all type I and type II countries (RCI_{I+II}).

$$S_{PROV,i} = S_{PROV,I+II} \times \frac{RCI_i}{RCI_{I+II}} \quad (21)$$

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ANNEX – RESULTS FOR ALL COUNTRIES

Country	Fair Share of Support or 'Recipient	Oil					Coal					Gas				
		Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence			Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence			Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence		
				E	R	J			E	R	J			E	R	J
United States	48.5%	2031	81%	36%	<1%	<1%	2031	83%	10%	n/a	<1%	2031	81%	33%	<1%	<1%
European Union	21.4% *															
Japan	8.7%						2030	83%	<1%	n/a	<1%					
Germany	6.2% *						2031	82%	10%	n/a	<1%	2031	83%	1%	n/a	<1%
United Kingdom	4.5%	2031	79%	21%	<1%	<1%	2030	83%	<1%	n/a	<1%	2031	80%	19%	<1%	<1%
France	3.9% *															
Canada	3.8%	2031	78%	30%	1%	1%	2031	83%	3%	n/a	<1%	2031	79%	31%	<1%	<1%
Australia	3.1%	2031	82%	14%	<1%	<1%	2031	78%	26%	n/a	2%	2031	78%	25%	<1%	2%
Italy	2.6% *	2031	82%	3%	n/a	<1%						2031	82%	2%	n/a	<1%
Netherlands	1.7% *											2031	81%	15%	n/a	<1%
South Korea	1.6%						2030	83%	<1%	n/a	<1%					
Spain	1.6% *						2030	83%	<1%	n/a	<1%					
Switzerland	1.1%															
Saudi Arabia	1.1%	2041	27%	62%	49%	4%						2034	59%	38%	9%	<1%
Türkiye	1.0%						2031	78%	12%	n/a	<1%					
Norway	0.9%	2030	83%	19%	13%	6%						2030	83%	8%	16%	7%
Belgium	0.9% *															
Sweden	0.9% *															
United Arab Emirates	0.8%	2033	64%	43%	42%	3%						2032	75%	41%	11%	<1%
Ireland	0.8% *															
Denmark	0.7% *	2031	82%	19%	n/a	<1%						2031	82%	8%	n/a	<1%
Austria	0.6% *															
Qatar	0.6%	2031	77%	30%	22%	5%						2032	73%	70%	29%	9%
Singapore	0.5%															
Kuwait	0.5%	2037	40%	50%	54%	7%						2032	74%	30%	4%	<1%
Taiwan	0.5%															
Israel	0.4%															
Finland	0.4% *															
New Zealand	0.4%						2031	82%	5%	n/a	<1%					
Greece	0.3% *						2031	80%	6%	n/a	<1%					
Chile	0.3%															
Czech Republic	0.2% *						2032	68%	29%	n/a	<1%					
Portugal	0.2% *															

Country	Fair Share of Support or 'Recipient	Oil					Coal					Gas				
		Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence			Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence			Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence		
				E	R	J			E	R	J			E	R	J
Luxembourg	0.2% *															
Bahrain	<0.1%											2050	54%	26%	n/a	2%
Slovakia	<0.1% *															
Slovenia	<0.1% *															
Brunei	<0.1%	2033	63%	26%	6%	5%						2035	49%	26%	12%	10%
Lithuania	<0.1% *															
Estonia	<0.1% *															
Iceland	<0.1%															
Cyprus	<0.1% *															
Monaco	<0.1%															
Malta	<0.1% *															
Liechtenstein	<0.1%															
Guyana	<0.1%															
Andorra	<0.1%															
San Marino	<0.1%															
Cook Islands	<0.1%															
Poland	R *						2034	60%	40%	n/a	<1%	2031	81%	3%	n/a	<1%
Trinidad and Tobago	R	2033	64%	8%	5%	1%						2049	15%	92%	30%	9%
Hungary	R *						2031	80%	3%	n/a	<1%					
Libya	R	2050	11%	26%	78%	7%						2038	38%	26%	19%	2%
Oman	R	2045	20%	30%	45%	2%						2045	20%	69%	33%	2%
China	R	2031	80%	5%	<1%	<1%	2034	57%	55%	n/a	<1%	2031	80%	5%	<1%	<1%
Brazil	R	2034	58%	37%	4%	<1%	2031	82%	<1%	n/a	<1%	2031	79%	6%	<1%	<1%
Gabon	R	2040	30%	26%	36%	4%										
Malaysia	R	2034	54%	23%	5%	<1%						2039	35%	37%	13%	<1%
Romania	R *	2032	72%	10%	n/a	<1%	2032	73%	10%	n/a	<1%	2034	58%	24%	n/a	<1%
Mexico	R	2037	42%	44%	14%	<1%	2031	82%	2%	n/a	<1%	2033	64%	17%	5%	<1%
Russia	R	2037	41%	24%	11%	<1%	2033	67%	11%	n/a	<1%	2040	31%	51%	12%	<1%
Kazakhstan	R	2041	29%	25%	24%	<1%	2037	39%	46%	n/a	<1%	2035	49%	25%	7%	<1%
Colombia	R	2035	51%	44%	1%	<1%	2031	77%	5%	n/a	<1%	2033	68%	20%	<1%	<1%
South Africa	R						2040	30%	69%	n/a	<1%					
Argentina	R	2037	43%	38%	2%	<1%						2037	41%	42%	2%	<1%
Bulgaria	R *						2035	54%	30%	n/a	<1%					
Peru	R	2033	62%	21%	n/a	<1%						2034	54%	29%	n/a	<1%
Azerbaijan	R	2042	27%	35%	27%	<1%						2050	21%	62%	25%	<1%
Equatorial Guinea	R	2050	9%	26%	80%	3%										
Thailand	R	2032	69%	13%	n/a	<1%	2031	80%	3%	n/a	<1%	2033	63%	18%	n/a	<1%
Ecuador	R	2045	20%	67%	24%	<1%										

Country	Fair Share of Support or 'Recipient	Oil					Coal					Gas				
		Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence			Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence			Phaseout Year	Reduction in 2030 (%)	Dependence		
				E	R	J			E	R	J			E	R	J
Turkmenistan	R	2034	55%	18%	n/a	<1%						2050	14%	82%	n/a	4%
Iran	R	2040	31%	30%	21%	<1%						2046	19%	68%	26%	<1%
Serbia	R						2034	57%	26%	n/a	<1%					
Iraq	R	2050	8%	69%	85%	2%						2033	63%	15%	3%	<1%
Bolivia	R											2038	38%	26%	14%	<1%
Indonesia	R	2033	66%	13%	3%	<1%	2037	42%	45%	n/a	<1%	2033	62%	14%	5%	<1%
Zimbabwe	R						2034	58%	26%	n/a	<1%					
Algeria	R	2050	24%	35%	18%	2%						2048	16%	65%	22%	2%
Tunisia	R	2034	57%	26%	n/a	<1%										
Mongolia	R						2038	38%	26%	n/a	2%					
Venezuela	R	2042	25%	24%	36%	<1%	2031	83%	<1%	n/a	<1%	2043	24%	48%	27%	<1%
Egypt	R	2035	51%	30%	<1%	<1%						2039	34%	55%	1%	<1%
Uzbekistan	R	2031	76%	6%	<1%	<1%	2031	80%	3%	n/a	<1%	2043	23%	82%	8%	<1%
Nigeria	R	2039	33%	26%	25%	<1%						2037	44%	26%	13%	<1%
India	R	2031	75%	4%	2%	<1%	2036	45%	41%	n/a	<1%	2031	77%	3%	1%	<1%
Angola	R	2048	16%	26%	60%	1%										
Vietnam	R	2032	74%	8%	n/a	<1%	2034	59%	25%	n/a	<1%	2031	77%	6%	n/a	<1%
Sudan	R	2037	42%	26%	15%	<1%										
Congo, Republic of the	R	2044	21%	26%	33%	2%										
Ukraine	R						2032	68%	15%	n/a	<1%	2034	56%	27%	n/a	<1%
Myanmar	R											2034	56%	26%	n/a	<1%
Bangladesh	R											2036	44%	47%	n/a	<1%
Pakistan	R						2031	78%	5%	n/a	<1%	2034	56%	29%	n/a	<1%
Syria	R	2034	58%	26%	n/a	<1%						2034	58%	26%	n/a	<1%
South Sudan	R	2050	13%	26%	86%	<1%										
Chad	R	2041	27%	26%	37%	<1%										
Yemen	R	2034	58%	26%	n/a	<1%						2034	59%	26%	n/a	<1%

Notes: "Dependence" column shows the components of the composite measure of dependence, dependence on extraction for domestic energy (E), on revenue (R), and on jobs (J). The entry for the European Union is provided for convenience and shows the sum of the support provision percentages of all type I and type II EU member states; phaseout years differ between fossil-fuel-extracting EU members (EU and member states are marked with an asterisk in the "Fair Share of Support" column). Where no results are given for any country for any specific fuel, this country is not a major extractor of this fuel (see footnote 6). Where no results are given for any country for all fuels, this is a type II country and therefore only the percentage of support provision is given.